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Role of National Library of India in Preservation and Promoting Reading Habit

ABSTRACT

The study is the first of its kind in ascertaining the role that National Library plays in promoting reading habits among its users. Reading is significant for mental stimulation, developing intellectual skills, memory improvement, stress reduction. In the modern era, an era driven by technology, the upcoming generations are outrunning the reading habit. Libraries strive on reading. Libraries become more answerable to knowledge society for their role in inculcating reading habits in this scenario. National Library is also expected to deliver in this direction. The role of various sections of libraries has been discussed based on usage statistics. The paper concludes with expectations on policy reforms to further add value to National Library services. The amendment to policies will lead to better display, capturing users' attention, improvement in services, upkeep, and preservation of library resources. Along with this promotion of Indian languages, user-friendly practices and cooperation of networked agencies will get an uplift.

KEYWORDS:

National Library, India, National Library of India, Reading habit, Reading culture, Reading promotion

1 INTRODUCTION

Information management has been largely identified as a domain associated with Libraries and Library professionals. The library professionals are trained in selection and acquisition of reputed information sources, organising, repackaging and dissemination of information to serve users. They are also experts in preserving it for future use. In the age of digital environment, libraries are witnessing decline in physical visits to their premises. Also, in addition, digital devices are putting an end to reading habits in addition to decreased retention capacity of brain. This turns out to be a challenge for the libraries devoid of providing remote access to its resources. Libraries should serve their users with a combination of conventional library and virtual services to increase the footfall and promote the habit of reading in its users. Reading is defined as having read books (excel text books), news, magazines, reports (in any format: print or online) and online articles. A

conference on “The development of public libraries in Africa” was held in 1953, where the role of libraries was articulated in mass education programmes, stimulating reading interests and guidance for attaining new skills. Promotion of reading habit/culture has also been recognised as a core function of National Libraries. There are 351 National Libraries around the globe. India has one National Library, located at Kolkata and is functional under Delivery of Books and Newspapers Act (1956).

The National Library, India is the largest library of the nation equipped with mammoth size of reading materials; highly qualified professionals; readers from all categories, age groups and strata of society. The library has its birth evolved from Calcutta Public Library, which also played a significant role in Library movement in India. His excellency, Lord Curzon in a quest to establish a rich library, in 1902 combined collections of Calcutta Public Library with those of Official Imperial Library and number of secretariat libraries. The Imperial library was thrown open to public in 1903. With independence in 1947, the National Library came into existence when the Imperial Library (Change of Name) Act was passed in 1948. In conformity to Article 62 of the Seventh Schedule of the Union List of the Constitution of India, Library was accorded a status of an Institution of National importance.

The role of libraries in promoting reading culture has not been studied for National Libraries of developing or underdeveloped nations. A few studies on National Library of Bulgaria, though about reading habits are not much concentrated on this core topic have been dealt from a perspective of emerging technologies, digital environment. Also, for reading habits of Poland a study was conducted in 1975 and 1982 by the Institute of the Book and Reading Habits, The National Library, Warsaw on a large scale to come out with the usage of books in libraries. Circulation, loans, frequency of reading, reading population, bookshops availability was considered parameters to measure the role. Any such study exploring the role of National Library, India in context of promoting reading culture is evasive from the scene.

To bridge this gap, this study was carried at National Library of India. The study considered various sections of National Library that can influence the reading culture/habit among its users’. The relevance of Display section in capturing attention of users, has been explored. Lending

section with its circulation figures has also been considered. In addition to these, various Newspaper Sections: English Newspaper Section; Hindi & Bengali Bound Newspaper Section and Old Newspaper Section statistics have also been considered to arrive at their significance in promoting reading among library members. The study combines all these factors to ascertain the role of National Library in achieving one of its core functions of promoting reading habits among various categories of users'. It is expected that the study will help to measure performance, paving way for future plans, constructing strategies resulting in delivering of library services more efficiently.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The cumulative case studies belonging to National Libraries of Australia, Canada, France, Germany, Jamaica, Korea, Netherlands, New Zealand, Romania, Singapore, and British Library, were undertaken by Stephens in an attempt to propose up-to-date guidelines for National Libraries by IFLA. Reference to promotion of reading among youth has been mentioned for Korea's National Library for Children and Young Adults (NLCYA, opened in June 2006). Similarly, TD Summer Reading Club run by Toronto Public Library in collaboration with others is an award-winning programme oriented towards encouraging reading among children and their families. The National Library of Nigeria along with other national institutions identifies itself with the responsibility to promote reading among citizens. Also, they have the responsibility to encourage the production of reading material and identify obstacles in creation of reading environment in the country. However, the National Library of Nigeria in the absence of funding has failed to promote its Readership campaigns in print and electronic media beyond major cities.

The supporting and flourishing reading networks attract newer members from varied backgrounds to Public Libraries. Libraries provide space, reading material, staff assistance, arranges events and activities and brings together communities through reading programmes.

A reading survey undertaken by National Library of Poland found that reading is on ever-decreasing trend with all age groups. The author carried his own survey among 400 student respondents of lower or upper secondary levels. Findings reveal that around 71% do not prefer reading even during leisure time. For assignments, 85% depend on internet, while none of the respondents recognised library as the main source of information. The author has mentioned numerous initiatives and ways through which reading has been encouraged by Polish libraries, for

instance holding exhibitions, reading by celebrities for children at picnics etc. In agreement to UNESCO Public Library Manifesto 1994, Otiye has mentioned objectives of Public library of Kenya with special reference to promotion of reading culture. The Public library should organise exhibitions and fairs to attract users to collections. The author has also discussed challenges faced by libraries in promoting reading habits. Free library services should be introduced to reduce the gap between information rich and poor. The importance and trend of reading habits witnessed for countries participating in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) Test has been discussed by Adkins and Brendler. The study reveals that reading is turning into a limited habit globally. The author has suggested that libraries should introduce literature circle to encourage reading for those with poor reading skills to spend more time on reading. The author in his study mentioned setting up of National Mission on Libraries in India. The Mission was proposed to develop in setting quality standards, acquiring books, adopt digitisation, mobilise community by undertaking reaching out activities, fostering reading habit and conducting periodic surveys to assess user needs. National Library Mission was approved in November 2013 under the Ministry of Culture. Six Libraries under the Ministry of Culture were selected in its first phase to be developed as Model Libraries. Upgrade of infrastructure, ICT facilities, networking and creating these facilities differently abled person friendly were the focus. National Library, Kolkata was allocated 400 lakh rupees to modernise it.

3. OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the study is to explore the role of National Library in promoting and strengthening reading habits of its users through diverse services that the organization offers. Taking this into consideration, following specific objectives were framed:

1. To examine role of various sections of National Library in promoting reading habits among users'
2. To investigate the challenges faced by Library staff in promoting reading culture.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To meet the objectives, multiple personal visits were undertaken to National Library premises. The data was collected in mid-2019. The main purpose of the study was to identify the role of various divisions of National Library in promoting reading culture. For achieving the objectives, monthly

reports from National Library (regarding exhibiting/usage statistics) were collected for (i) Display section (ii) Lending section (iii) Newspaper Section – English; Old Newspaper; and Hindi and Bengali Bound Newspaper Section. The usage statistics were then entered in Excel sheet and charts were constructed to see the variation during various months. The qualitative method was employed using non-structured interview method to identify the challenges faced by officials of concerned sections.

In addition to reports, interview method, the researcher has used observation as a tool during a visit to supplement the required information. Random users were also interviewed to know their take on measures that should be adopted by concerned sections under study. Several challenges were faced by the researcher during collection and analysis of data. National Library though maintains monthly reports the indicators are not maintained in uniformity over the same year for the same section. Further, for few months, the reports by concerned divisions are unavailable. However, with an intent to outline the reading promotion, the study was conducted.

5. Data Analysis and Interpretation

5.1 To study the usage of various sections indicating role of Library in addressing reading needs of users'

5.1.1 Display Section: Displays in the library are effective in the usage of collection. Libraries use display places to advertise about new arrivals, special collections, upcoming events, promoting programmes. They work as alerting mechanism for users. The display areas are either designated near the main entrance of Library or in reading rooms itself to gain maximum attention. For National Library, India, display section turns more pertinent. It acts as a marketing agent, an insight to collection it holds owing to the library's closed access nature. National Library of India carries display in Main Reading Room housed in Bhasha Bhawan. The reading room has a seating capacity of 160 seats. The display area is utilised for new books and periodicals in English and in different Indian languages. Libraries display only book covers or jackets, but as per the policy at National Library whole document is displayed.

To gain insight into functioning and the process of exhibiting documents in Reading Room, a non-structured interview method was adopted. This library staff apprised that Forty English book titles have the reservation to be exhibited in Display area. Acquisition (Book Selection) forwards these titles (English language) to the main reading room. For English periodical display, forty monthly titles of periodicals are sent by the English Serial Division of the library. The display section has the responsibility of collection of books and periodicals on Indian Language Divisions and forwarding the same reading room for display at its new arrival section. A total of ten books and fifteen periodicals from each Indian language division are displayed to promote reading of Indian languages. However, at times owing to some administrative reasons books and periodicals, instead of being routed through the display unit, are received directly from some Indian Language Divisions.

2019	ENGLISH LANGUAGE received for display		INDIAN LANGUAGES received for display		
	Books newly displayed	Periodicals newly displayed	Books and Periodicals newly displayed	Books and Periodicals redisplayed	Books and Periodicals displayed and withdrawn
Jan	35	39	0	0	0
Feb	35	39	0	0	0
March	40	50	0	242	0
April	42	44	0	149	0
May	42	44	177	54	218
June	41	0	157	117	90
July	42	40	181	25	305
Aug	130	0	40	141	40
Sep	42	40	0	181	0
Oct	40	40	20	181	60
Nov	90	40	40	181	100
Dec	60	38	15	161	15

Table 5.1(a) above shows the number of documents displayed (English and Indian Languages) and withdrawn (Indian Languages)

Indian Languages: The monthly reports of January and February 2019 for Indian Languages were not submitted by the display unit to their central collection point; hence, data for these 2 months are not available. To cater to readers from multilingual backgrounds at National Library, 630

items of varied Indian Languages were displayed against redisplay of 1432 items. Also, 828 items were withdrawn from the display during 2019. As evident from Table 5.1, July 2019 witnessed display of maximum fresh titles i.e., 181 and minimum redisplay i.e., only 25 titles redisplayed. Also, during the same month maximum titles i.e., 305 were withdrawn. In confirmation of same, during March, the highest number of titles i.e., 242 were redisplayed without any fresh addition or withdrawal. The display area saw 30.55% of fresh title display of Indian languages, whereas redisplay was counted to 69.44% of total display. The same were observed during personal physical visit to the display area. Most of the titles were not recent and were not properly displayed.

Fig 5.1(a) shows the number of documents in English language (Books and periodicals) displayed in Reading Room, National Library of India, Kolkata for the year 2019.

English Language: Fig 5.1 represents that 639 new titles of books and 414 journals from English Language were displayed. August recorded the maximum number of book displays (130 titles). Overall, except June'19 and August'19 where none of the new periodicals was displayed in English Language, the display was nearly carried effectively as per the policy briefed above (display of 40 titles for books and periodicals each) for the rest of year.

5.1.2 Lending Section: Highlighting the importance of Lending Section an observation was made by Kolodziejaska¹⁴ in his study. The study advocated the extent and effectiveness of library service measurement from the magnitude of book use i.e., from the circulation in society. Similarly, a characteristic feature of mass readership in Poland is a high percentage of loans from public

libraries. The following table reflects the lending section figures of National Library of India for 2019.

2019	LENDING SECTION			
	Local	Outstation	Intra library or Officials	International Loan request
Jan	230	0	4	0
Feb	194	0	2	1
March	266	0	0	1
April	253	0	2	1
May	269	0	0	1
June	265	0	2	0
July	235	0	0	0
Aug	154	0	0	0
Sep	213	0	1	0
Oct	231	0	0	0
Nov	236	0	0	0
Dec	220	0	0	0

Table 5.1 (b) represents the no. of documents issued by Lending section

The main function of the Lending Section is to issue books to borrowing members and government departments, recognised institutions, libraries. The lending of documents is handled centrally by Lending section. The lending section remains open on all weekdays from 9 a.m. to 8 p.m. and from 9.30a.m to 6 p.m. on Saturdays, Sundays and notified holidays. The library remains closed entirely on National holidays i.e., January 26, August 15 and October.

Fig 5.1 (b) shows the Lending record (Local users’) for the year 2019.

The reader at National Library can choose not to be a member of Lending Library. In such a case, the reader is not entitled to borrowing of books, but can avail in-house consultation of resources. To be a member of lending library, the reader must compulsorily deposit for security money. The security money can be deposited in cash/cheque. When the reader applies for withdrawal of membership, the security deposit is refunded by cheque. A registered member of lending library at any given time can borrow two books at maximum against the security deposit. In case the cost of books exceeds the security deposit, a reader must enhance security deposit. For Indian titles, books published/revised within the last 20 years are eligible to be lent out. Publications, that are more than 100 years old or received under gift and exchange, can only be borrowed by registered members against security fee. For foreign publications, only those publications that are in the active record in the Online Books-in-Print Catalogue are issued. Books are issued to Govt departments and other renowned departments on furnishing written request without any deposit. The National Library also facilitates inter-library loans, for which instructions are issued from time to time. During 2019, 2766 books were issued, while 11 were issued to intra-library or officials. The highest number of books (269) was issued during May, while the lowest (154) in August. The months of February, March, April, and May reports also show that one document each for the

mentioned months was requested for International Library loan and were replied on email. However, there is no record for acceptance/decline of the same. The data from lending section also shows that 33 requests for already issued documents were placed, only 8 borrowers were informed of reserved title availability.

5.1.3 Newspaper Section: The National Library is the implementing agency of the Delivery of Books and Newspapers (Public Libraries) Act 1956 and mandated to collect, disseminate and preserve all printed materials produced in India and all foreign works published about the country, by Indians abroad for preservation and posterity. Under the Act, all the Indian Publishers are legally bound to deposit one copy of the publication to the library.

‘Newspaper’ means any printed periodical work containing public news or comments on public news, published in conformity with the provisions of Section 5 of the Press and Registration of Books Act, 1867. Reading newspapers in addition to giving educational support brings in improvement towards reading skills. Newspapers are unbound publications that help in updating local, provincial, national and international events. Newspapers often cover wide issues political, social, sports, entertainment, opinion columns, editorials, caricatures, weather information, zodiac forecasts.

The old Newspaper Reading Room at National Library houses a rich collection of 19th and 20th century newspapers, including Bengalee (1863), Friend of India (1838), Hindoo Patriot (1854), Englishman (1837), Amrita Bazar Patrika (1886), The Statesman (1923), Liberty (1929), Mussalman (1906), John Bull (1823), Advance (1931), Anglo-Indian Recorder (1912), Indian Observer (1871) and Indian Mirror (1883). The library has also “Hicky’s Gazette”, the first newspaper in India in its collection. A total of 98 English titles and 43 titles in other languages of Indian newspapers were received by the library under D.B. Act. The usage of English Newspaper Division, Hindi and Bengali unbound Newspaper Division and Old Newspaper division is presented below in Figures.

Fig 5.1.3(a) shows usage of newspapers in English Newspaper Reading Room

Fig 5.1.3(b) shows usage of newspapers in Hindi & Bengali unbound Newspaper Division

Fig 5.1.3 (c) shows the usage of newspapers in Old Newspaper Division

2019	No. of readers attended	No. of vol's supplied	Average vol's supplied per reader
English Newspaper Division	1657	858	1.93
Hindi and Bengali unbound Newspaper Division	309	6979	22.58
Old Newspaper Division	843	1306	1.54

Table 5.1.3 depicting annual usage of newspapers in all three divisions

The maximum-used newspaper section belongs to Hindi and Bengali, the probable reason for the same may be that Bengali being the regional language and people visiting National Library in routine are from nearby areas and well versed with the language. Old Newspaper Division has showed the lowest usage amongst three, for probably the old newspapers is accessed only by people who are either researchers, historians or working on a particular project/story. This category of users is predominantly interested in-depth research of the topic and information contained in a secondary source of information.

While English Newspaper section has probably least usage amongst all as evident from various studies that people Nowadays are lagging on reading habits and prefer digital format while on go 24x7. Various studies have agreed to the role of newspaper in promoting reading habits. Audu considered Newspapers as best means to strengthen reading habits of individuals. News reading, for 2017, has been credited to be the most popular reading practice (in both formats: print and digital) in study related to reading habits of Poland. A study carried at Dhaka University measured effects of reading English newspapers in improving reading skills employing convenient sampling technique. The respondents completely favoured newspaper as a means to promote reading. A study carried at Varanasi showed that 80% respondents preferred reading hard copy (print format) of Hindi newspapers even in the digital age. In January 2019, National Library organised two events in collaboration with The Hindu Newspaper- Quiz and Painting Competition. The then Director of National Library interacted with 350 student participants and delivered a lecture on “Inculcating Reading Habits”.

5.2 To discuss the challenges faced by Library staff in promoting reading culture.

5.2.1 Display Area: The staff during interaction apprised the challenges faced at National Library. Most of the challenges have aroused due to long back formulated policies, with no revisions in the recent past. The officials were aware of users’ often express their discontent with the upkeep of display area and raised concerns over exhibited material. The fault is traced to the long typing procedure that display materials must cover to reach display area. The books are received under the Delivery of Books and Newspapers Act, 1956 at sorting unit of the Central Registry Section. The sorting unit segregates the books into bundles depending on the language. These bundles are then sent to their respective language division. The concerned language division sends acknowledgements to publishers/authors for their receipt. The books before being sent to the display unit for display in reading room are allotted Accession number. The documents are sent for display post accessioning and are kept in display area for 1 month. Due to the existing system of transit of books from one unit to another and presence of skeletal staff in individual language divisions, there is a significant delay in the display of titles. This whole elongated process results in defeating the aim and purpose of displaying the newly arrived books at Bhasha Bhawan Reading Room.

5.2.2 Lending Section: After the expiry of the display period, the displayed documents are withdrawn and sent back to concerned divisions for further processing and finally finding way to stacks for circulation and consultation. In an event of inability of any division/section to arrange for fresh display of titles due to any reason, the titles already displayed are redisplayed for another display cycle. In case of request for issuing of displayed title by a registered member, the staff plays proactive role in meeting the users' requirement. On completion of display period and withdrawal of requested title from display area, concerned division is informed about the request. The title in question is processed on priority and made available to users for issuing at reading room or lending library. The period that goes in technical processing after 1 month of display and in some cases redisplay, consumes a lot of time, resulting in furthering delay of reaching documents to stacks. As the library follows closed access, a user should consult Web OPAC and fill the required information in requisition slip. The slip is then handed to the staff present at the counter, who provides the required document after bringing it from stacks. This affects lending of desired titles to users, as in some cases it may take a lot of time or that title goes untraced or that a user hesitates to place the demand for several titles. A study conducted concluded that there is a significant relationship between books borrowed from institutional library and student's academic grades. Bamberger also supported the idea that borrowing books from public libraries or friends leads to lifelong reading habits in his paper "Promoting the reading habit".

Lending of books along with other such programmes are provided in school libraries to encourage voluntary reading habits among students. The findings of the study made it evident that lending of books has a significant relationship with voluntary reading habits. The staff at the National Library feels filling vacant posts should be taken up on priority to handle the quantum of work. This will help in providing services effectively leading to satisfaction of users' needs.

5.2.3 Newspaper Section: The major challenge that is faced by the National Library is contempt by Publishing houses. Ideally, National Library is bound to receive all newspapers under Delivery of Books Act, 1956 with a motive to preserve literary sources of the country. In reality, all newspapers published in the country are not sent to a repository, resulting in incompleteness in the collection. Further those newspapers that are received, are not handled properly due to lack of arrangements like humidity control. This leads to decay and damage of newspapers. The ideal storage condition of 18° C to 20°C temperature and 50% -55% relative humidity through air

conditioning is to be maintained. Also, as per rule all the newspapers should be preserved by way of binding and microfilming at regular intervals to elongate their life span. Only a few old English Newspapers are microfilmed, while those of Hindi, Bengali or other regional languages are not processed for digital preservation. Microfilming of regional language newspapers also pose a challenge to the library with limited personnel. The records from Preservation and Reprography division also reflect that at many times, they are out of stock of film rolls and other equipment required to carry digital preservation. The poor quality of paper and ink used in publishing newspapers further demand their immediate preservation. The records from Newspaper Section present a scenario where newspapers are received by the National Library in bundles and not on an everyday basis. Adding to this is a huge shortfall of semi-professional staff for the proper maintenance and service of the newspapers. Their scattering, sorting, processing further takes times as in case of books and periodicals. The newspapers thus may remain effective for people who are in research, historians, journalists or other such activities, but not for users' who visit the library for recreational purposes, update their knowledge, prepare for competitive exams etc. due to delayed arrival. The restoration of newspapers is urgently required to put deplorable condition of Newspaper Section in control.

6.0 Discussion:

Display areas increases the visibility of titles, helps in users select their next read by overcoming information overload otherwise. at National Library, Display area should be introduced at the entrance as all users visiting Library do not head to reading room only. This will help capture more readership, increased circulation of books and optimum use of resources. The importance of Display Area has been successfully highlighted in the study performed at Brigham Young University (BYU) located in Provo, Utah. An increase of 58.2% was recorded in the circulation of displayed titles. Similarly, an increase of 323.4% in usage frequency was recorded for less popular titles compared to 18% usage increase for popular books. The Library may use the Indian Writers' Gallery for display and promotion of various Indian languages. The gallery can carry displays motivated by significant days, authors, prominent events from each language. Such display can be of fixed duration of 3 months or so, which should be notified to its members through Email/SMS/push notifications. The website may also flash the theme displays along with the

timetable of such display for the information of the public. The link to bibliographical details of such displayed documents should be stored in archives section on website so that interested future readers may take benefit from these. The registration area/lobby should have digital images of cover pages of books along with their bibliographical details running on LEDs to make users aware about new arrivals. The website can also include this feature to attract readers. The registration area is spacious and can be utilised in a way to push reading culture in users. In the times of publication explosion and National Library being the custodian of treasure of literary work in the country, it becomes even more significant for Library professionals to understand the requirements of their users and put into effective use of book displays. This will promote the usage of the vast collection and encourage reading habits among users. Further, various Indian languages can work in better coordinated way with Display Section to avoid redisplay of titles. Author corners can be created so that book launches, excerpt reads, critical analysis can be organised by the National Library/Publishing houses. This can also act as revenue generating activity. It has been observed that outstation, intra library and international library loans are near negligible. National Library having plethora of information literary sources at its disposal should encourage borrowing by other public or more appropriately research libraries from its treasure, so as to reduce financial burden on individual organisations. A network of libraries should be created with National Library at its apex to meet demands of such organisations at local level. Norms should be relaxed for outstation visitors to encourage borrowing of documents. The documents that show lesser circulation as per usage statistics, with co-operation of lending section and display section should find its way to display area so that third law of library science “Every book its reader” may be achieved. The Library authority should take a policy decision to review the issue of not lending the Indian language books that are more than 20 years old. These criteria forbid most borrowers to use the lending facility and therefore find it discouraging. This is also in contrast to first three laws of Library Science devised by Dr. S.R.Ranganathan.

The Library authority should introduce UPI payments to remove the hurdles in payment of security deposits/ penalty for late return of books to facilitate borrowing the books from the library and also encourage users to get membership to the Lending Library. Most of the borrowers interviewed aired their discontent regarding the working of cash hours. The readers felt till UPI payments are introduced in the Library, the cash counter should be kept open for longer hours on week days. The readers also supported the opening of transactions for Lending Library on Saturdays, Sundays

and other holidays. The Library needs to put more efforts in physical and digital preservation of newspapers. The National Library to counter the decay and damage of newspapers should reach an understanding with publishing/media houses. The Library should think of signing MoU with newspaper agencies to send the soft copy of newspapers belonging to all languages to National Library. These can be digitally preserved. The digital preservation ensures proper storage, adequate maintenance and usability over time. The available staff can use time in more productive attention desiring activities like dealing with archival volumes and their preservation. The readers facing problems due to non-availability of current newspapers will also be dealt through this arrangement. For the users' who prefer print format, the Library should propose including provision and budget for daily purchase of select popular newspapers for usage and promoting reading habit, by bringing change in purchase policy.

CONCLUSION

Reading habit helps in shaping personality, improving thought process, guaranteeing academic success etc. Various studies conducted witnessed decline in reading habits among new generation. this world age is no longer relying on traditional modes only. The study conducted has called attention to the role of the National Library in promoting reading habit among the citizens of country. The researcher has found that National Library is no longer acting as last resort for researchers only but readership base comes from a wider base of information seekers. They rely on abundant resources available at the National Library for fulfilling their information needs. The study also concludes that the National should revise its policies regarding display, lending of documents, procurement of newspapers to motivate its readers for developing reading culture and increase resource usage. National Library should also consider adopting latest technology in achieving the increased readership by promotion of reading materials.

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